

**POSSIBILITIES OF MULTIPARAMETRIC PRENATAL ECHOCARDIOGRAPHY IN THE
DIAGNOSIS OF FETAL VENTRICULAR SEPTAL DEFECT**

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Abstract

The aim of the research improvement of ultrasound diagnostics of fetal ventricular septal defect during the prenatal period through the application of innovative multiparametric extended antenatal transabdominal echocardiography methods. In the study involved 4800 pregnant women who underwent a comprehensive examination during the period from 2022 to 2023 at the Maternal and Child Health Center. Among them, 150 pregnant women had fetal heart pathology, including 38 patients with isolated VSD in the fetus. After birth, 29 children born with isolated VSD were monitored, and 27 children were hospitalized for surgical treatment at the National Children's Medical Center with isolated VSD. The control group consisted of 30 healthy children. The age of the children with VSD examined ranged from 1 month to 6 months.

In the results the effectiveness of the developed technology of multiparametric extended antenatal fetal echocardiography using STIC and Speckle tracking methods has been proven; risk factors in pregnant women that indicate the use of comprehensive innovative fetal echocardiography methods at 18-22 weeks of gestation have been identified; multiparametric detailed echographic semiotics of fetal VSD depending on the size and variant of defect location has been proven; reliable scientifically substantiated clinical-laboratory and echographic parallels that depend on the size and variant of VSD location have been established.

Keywords: CHD, newborns, VSD, antenatal echography, pregnant women, STIC.

Introduction. Progress in diagnostic methods in developed countries such as the USA, Canada, the UK, Germany, and Japan has significantly improved the diagnosis of VSD (Ventricular Septal Defect) through the introduction of multiparametric prenatal echocardiography. This method combines traditional 2D echocardiography with Doppler and 3D/4D techniques, allowing for more detailed imaging of the fetal heart and more accurate assessment of its structure and function. In the USA, studies have shown that the use of multiparametric antenatal echocardiography with the application of 3D and 4D echocardiography significantly increases the accuracy of VSD diagnosis. Research at leading medical centers, such as the University of California, San Francisco (UCSF) and Boston Children's Hospital, has demonstrated that multiparametric echocardiography can detect even small defects that may be missed using only 2D methods.

Congenital heart defects (CHDs) are recognized as the most common congenital pathologies, affecting 1 in 100 newborns and being a major cause of infant mortality [2]. According to authors, VSDs account for 20-30% to 40-50% of all CHDs, with a frequency of 41.8 per 10,000 live births [2]. With the advent of prenatal ultrasonography in the 1980s and echocardiography in the 1990s [1], the detection rate of CHDs, particularly

VSDs, has increased due to the improvement in prenatal and postnatal screening tests, which also enhance the detection of anatomical variants without clinical consequences. Currently, prenatal diagnosis of heart defects is enhanced with 4D echocardiography, implemented using STIC (spatio-temporal image correlation) technology [3]. As the abbreviation implies, STIC provides multiplanar representation and volumetric visualization of moving structures such as the fetal heart [4].

The aim of the study was to improve the ultrasound diagnosis of fetal ventricular septal defect (VSD) during the prenatal period by applying innovative methods of multiparametric extended antenatal transabdominal echocardiography.

Materials and methods: Transabdominal fetal echocardiography was performed on 4800 pregnant women who visited the Mother and Child Health Center between 2022 and 2023, at gestational ages ranging from 11 to 38 weeks. The ultrasound anatomy data, standard heart views, and major vessels of the fetuses were thoroughly examined.

The age of the pregnant women varied from 18 to 45 years, with an average age of 31.5 years (Table 1). The control group consisted of 50 pregnant women without fetal pathology.

Table 1

Distribution of Pregnant Women by Age (n=150)

Age	Control group, n=50		CHD, n=150			VSD, n=38		
	Abs.	%	Abs.	%	P	Abs.	%	P
<20 лет	3	6,0%	12	8,0%		4	10,5%	
21-30 лет	17	34,0%	76	50,7%	P<0.05	18	47,4%	P<0.001
>31 лет	30	60,0%	62	41,3%	P<0.01	16	42,1%	P<0.001

Women younger than 20 years constituted 6%, those aged 21-30 years - 50.7%, and those older than 30 years - 42.1%. It is possible that the low frequency of VSD in women younger than 20 years is due to the small sample size of patients in this age group. In the age groups of 21-30 years and older than 30 years, the detection frequency of VSD was significantly higher and was approximately the same in these age groups. However, the increase in the frequency of CHD with maternal age is evident. The results of our studies are consistent with several researchers who claim that age matters in the development of heart anomalies in fetuses (Glyantsev S.P., Yazhborovskaya A.S., Gandzhaliev A.A., 2015, Wang Y., Fan M., Siddiqui F. et al., 2017).

When identifying the sex of the fetuses, there was no significant difference: 58.3% were boys and 41.7% were girls. In 150 cases, various cardiac defects were identified, of which 38 were VSDs. In the postnatal period, 31 newborns underwent echocardiography. In our study, we noted that a significant portion of the pregnant women were multiparous within the age range of 21-40 years, among whom CHDs in fetuses were diagnosed.

Risk indicators for targeted echocardiography are conditionally divided into indications on the part of the mother and on the part of the fetus.

Maternal indications:

- Age younger than 20 and older than 30 years;
- History of CHD in relatives or previous children with CHD;
- Maternal diabetes;
- Maternal infectious diseases;
- Exposure to teratogenic factors during pregnancy;
- Presence of severe somatic diseases.

Fetal indications:

- Polyhydramnios;

- Non-immune fetal hydrops;
- Extracardiac fetal anomalies;
- Cardiomegaly;
- Heart rhythm disturbances;
- Abnormal four-chamber heart view of the fetus;
- Markers of genetic abnormalities in the fetus;
- Intrauterine growth restriction.

The control group included 50 healthy pregnant women and 30 healthy children without congenital heart defects.

The study used high-end equipment, including the Aplio 500 (Japan), GE Logiq P7 (USA), GE Voluson E8 (USA), and Samsung Medison V8, with the specialized FetalHeart program. The examination was conducted using a volumetric convex (3D) probe with a frequency of 3.5 MHz and a high-frequency linear probe (9L).

The statistical analysis of the study results was conducted using methods of variation statistics with Microsoft Office Excel 2019 and IBM SPSS Statistics 26, calculating the standard deviation and the mean arithmetic error ($M \pm m$).

To determine the statistical significance of the obtained measurements for unrelated ranges, the non-parametric Mann-Whitney test was used, and for qualitative features, Fisher's exact test was applied.

Results.

Prevalence and Structure of Congenital Heart Defects According to Antenatal Screening Data

As a result of the study, heart pathology in fetuses was detected in 150 pregnant women, of which 38 patients were diagnosed with an isolated form of fetal VSD. Postnatal follow-up was conducted for 29 of these children, as well as for 27 children with isolated VSD who were hospitalized for surgical treatment at the National Children's Medical Center. The age of the examined children ranged from 1 to 6 months. The control group consisted of 30 healthy children.

Table 2

Number of Detected CHDs in Fetuses for 2022-2023

Year	Total examined	CHD		Of which isolated VSD	
		abs.n.	%	abs. n.	%
2022	1658	68	4,1	17	0,35
2023	3142	82	2,6	21	0,43
Total	4800	150	3,1	38	0,79

The structure of defects was diverse: VSD accounted for 25.3% of cases, the lowest number of cases was pulmonary valve atresia - 0.6%, and "other" defects accounted for 4.6%. Depending on the anatomical structure, the defect was most often located in the perimembranous part. Perimembranous VSD occurred in 14 (36.8%) cases, isolated muscular VSD in 8 (21.1%) cases. In 5 fetuses, spontaneous intrauterine closure was noted. Subaortic VSD was found in 10

cases (26.3%). Inflow VSD was observed in 5 cases (13.2%). An apical VSD was identified in one newborn (2.6%).

When analyzing the risk factors for CHD development, the main groups of causes were identified, including obstetric history and family history, maternal chronic diseases, and exposure to infections in the first trimester.

Table 3

Risk Factors for Fetal CHD					
Factors	Control group, n=50		Main group, n=150		Statistical Significance, P*
Obstetric and Gynecological History					
Age, years	25,3±5,0		28,2±4,5		>0,05
Pregnancy 1-2	4	8,0%	72	48,0%	<0,001
Pregnancy 3-4	16	32,0%	78	52,0%	<0,01
Premature births	1	2,0%	8	5,3%	>0,05
Stillbirths	0	0,0%	6	4,0%	>0,05
Non-developing pregnancy	1	2,0%	10	6,7%	>0,05
Family history					
CHD in mother	1	2,0%	13	8,7%	>0,05
CHD in father	1	2,0%	6	4,0%	>0,05
CHD in previous children	1	2,0%	5	3,3%	>0,05
Maternal Diseases					
Chronic liver disease	3	6,0%	18	12,0%	>0,05
Chronic kidney disease	5	10,0%	34	22,7%	<0,05
Systemic diseases	1	2,0%	23	15,3%	<0,01
Endocrinopathies	2	4,0%	29	19,3%	<0,01
Diabetes mellitus	1	2,0%	8	5,3%	>0,05
Features of Current Pregnancy					
Acute viral infections in the first trimester	4	8,0%	52	34,7%	<0,001
Rubella	1	2,0%	6	4,0%	>0,05
Chronic infection	2	4,0%	13	8,7%	>0,05
Polyhydramnios	2	4,0%	16	10,7%	>0,05
Oligohydramnios	1	2,0%	11	7,3%	>0,05
Intrauterine infection	5	10,0%	45	30,0%	<0,01

Note: * - values are significant in relation to the control group (p<0.05).

Family history, considering the presence of CHD in the pregnant woman herself and her family members, also showed statistical significance. Among chronic maternal diseases, the most significant was chronic pyelonephritis, which occurred in 22.7% of cases in the main group and 10.0% of cases in the control group (p<0.05). Analysis of the course of the current pregnancy in women of the main group revealed the impact of acute viral infections in the first trimester of pregnancy in 34.7% of cases, as well as the influence of intrauterine infections in 30.0% of cases compared to the control group (8% and 10%, respectively, p<0.05).

The assessment of risk factors identified the most significant factors in the development of fetal VSD. The five most significant groups of causes were determined to be specific features of obstetric and gynecological history, acute infectious diseases in the first trimester of pregnancy, chronic diseases, and the course of the current pregnancy.

We presented biometric parameters of the fetal heart in healthy pregnant women, based on anamnesis and ultrasound data. Normative indicators were determined for comparison with the main group.

Table 4

Biometric Indicators of Echographic Examination of the Fetal Heart in Subjects with Isolated VSD (M±m)

Indicator	Control		VSD		Mann-Whitney	P
	N	M±m	N	M±m		
LV	50	5,8±0,35	38	6,81±0,48	0,06851	
RV	50	5,9±0,35	38	6,4±0,46	0,19625	
LA	50	6,27±0,04	38	7,3±0,08	0,00000	P<0,001
RA	50	6,31±0,04	38	6,69±0,07	0,00000	P<0,001
LVOT	50	3,2±0,02	38	3,6±0,03	0,00000	P<0,001
DA	50	2,9±0,02	38	3,41±0,03	0,00000	P<0,001
LV/RV	50	1,01±0,01	38	1,02±0,01	0,20762	
RV/LV	50	2,45±0,15	38	2,39±0,18	0,37443	
LA/RA	50	1,01±0,01	38	1,03±0,02	0,40340	
RA/LA	50	0,99±0,01	38	0,98±0,01	0,18628	

Note: P<0.05 between control and VSD

Visualization of the fetal heart using STIC technology enhances the accuracy of CHD diagnosis due to its capabilities for multiplanar analysis and 3D reconstruction. We utilized a modern technological method of clinical investigation of the fetal heart with volumetric ultrasound image reconstruction (3D/4D), specifically the STIC technology, to assess the fetal heart condition in 30 pregnant women. We defined a control curve for the area of the interventricular septum using STIC-rendering mode. The active line (ROI) was placed at the outer edge of the interventricular septum, which was manually delineated. We evaluated 12 pregnant women at 18 to 33 weeks of gestation. A correlation between the area of the interventricular septum and gestational age was noted ($r=0.81$), with the average area increasing from 0.47 ± 0.1 cm² at 18 weeks to 2.42 ± 1.13 cm² at 33 weeks. Obtaining fetal heart data using 3D/4D ultrasonography with STIC software allows the identification of heart structures in the form of a 4D cine sequence, containing information about the entire cardiac cycle, thus combining spatial and temporal information. The assessment can be performed in both multiplanar mode and visualization mode, with accompanying color Doppler, tomographic ultrasound imaging, inversion mode, or B-flow visualization, or without them. Therefore, heart condition assessment can be conducted in the absence of the patient, as the analysis of the heart volume can be performed offline and by different experts. This increases the accuracy of two-dimensional echocardiography in diagnosing CHD. STIC in visualization mode allows direct measurement of the interventricular septum. Additionally, it enables the assessment of heart function in conjunction with virtual organ computer analysis software for calculating total systolic volume, ejection fraction, and cardiac output.

Thus, based on the above, 3D/4D STIC is a highly promising tool for obtaining qualitative and comprehensive volumetric data on the fetal heart. Trans-abdominal echocardiography using high-resolution ultrasound devices and modern technologies (special research modes and STIC) has increased the accuracy of fetal VSD diagnosis to 90.5%.

Examination of the four-chamber view of the heart and cross-sections through three vessels, as well as color Doppler mapping, allowed the detection of isolated VSD between 18-22 weeks of gestation. Speckle tracking is one of the modern methods that enables real-time evaluation of fetal myocardial movements. This technology uses special algorithms to track the movement of individual speckles on heart images, providing accurate data on myocardial function and deformation.

Before using 3D and Speckle Tracking technologies, it is necessary to conduct a standard fetal heart examination using B-mode and Doppler mapping for preliminary assessment of the heart's anatomy and function. The use of Speckle Tracking technology in combination with 3D visualization of the fetal heart opens up new possibilities for prenatal diagnosis of congenital heart defects. This approach not only allows for more precise identification of anatomical defects but also enables detailed functional analysis of the myocardium, significantly improving prognosis and outcomes for the fetus and newborn.

Clinical Parameters and Specificity of Ultrasound Indicators in Early-Age Children with VSD Before Surgery.

The study included two groups: the main group of 56 children with VSD and a control group of 30 healthy children of similar age and gender. To determine pre-operative tactics, all children underwent clinical and instrumental examinations.

Table 5

Main Parameters of Children in the Studied Groups at Birth

Parameters		Control group, n=30	Main group, n=56	P
Age, months, M±m		4,03±0,11	4,23±0,06	> 0,05
Gender	Boys, %	46,7	58,9	> 0,05
	Girls, %	53,3	41,1	
Birth weight, M ±m, г		3393,3±47,5	3023,2±29,7	<0,01

According to standard methods, the physical condition of the children was analyzed using the following ratios: weight/age, height/age, weight/length, and body mass index (BMI). The WHO programs for children under 5 years old were used for this purpose (WHO, 2006; Huang Y., Hsu K., Chuluunbaatar E. et al., 2018, Li X., Song G., Wu L. et al., 2016).

Upon admission for surgical treatment of VSD, the main complaints included: shortness of breath at rest and during exertion (feeding), sweating, underweight and insufficient weight gain, frequent respiratory infections, and cyanosis during crying.

The physical development parameters of the examined children are shown in Table 6.

Table 6.

The physical development parameters of the examined children						
Z-score (SD)	Control group, n=30		Main group, n=56		Fisher	P
Body length						
above3	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	
+2 +3	5	16,7%	2	3,6%	0,040843	P<0.05
+1 +2	7	23,3%	5	8,9%	0,050859	
0 (median +/-1)	15	50,0%	21	37,5%	0,097558	
-1 -2	2	6,7%	15	26,8%	0,017762	P<0.05
-2 -3	1	3,3%	11	19,6%	0,029215	P<0.05
below-3	0	0,0%	2	3,6%	0,421341	
Body weight						
above3	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	
+2 +3	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	
+1 +2	9	30,0%	4	7,1%	0,006038	P<0.01
0 (median +/-1)	18	60,0%	17	30,4%	0,005608	P<0.01
-1 -2	3	10,0%	18	32,1%	0,014994	P<0.05
-2 -3	0	0,0%	16	28,6%	0,000431	P<0.001
below -3	0	0,0%	1	1,8%	0,651163	
BMI						
Above +3	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	1	
+2 +3	2	6,7%	1	1,8%	0,23803	
+1 +2	7	23,3%	5	8,9%	0,050859	
0 (median +/-1)	17	56,7%	20	35,7%	0,032513	P<0.05
-1 -2	3	10,0%	20	35,7%	0,006748	P<0.01
-2 -3	1	3,3%	7	12,5%	0,131125	
-3	0	0,0%	4	7,1%	0,17296	

The table shows that the weight and length measurements of children in the main group were significantly lower than those in the control group. According to the WAZ criterion, 28.6% (16) of children with VSD in the main group had moderate undernutrition, and 32.1% (18) had mild undernutrition, compared to 10% (3) in the control group (p<0.001). The risk of overweight was noted in 30% (9) of children in the control group. According to the HAZ criterion, stunted growth was identified in 19.6% (11) of children in the main group compared to 3.3% (1) in the control group. At the same time, tall stature was observed in 16.7% (5) of children in the control group compared to 3.6% (2) in

the main group. BMI was lower in 35.7% (20) of children in the main group compared to 10% (3) in the control group, respectively.

Among the general clinical symptoms, perioral cyanosis was noted in both large and small defects, occurring in 34 (75.6%) and 6 (54.5%) cases, respectively. Dyspnea at rest was noted in 12 children (21.4%), while dyspnea with mild exertion was observed in 50 (89.2%) patients. Auscultation revealed a pansystolic murmur. A small ventricular septal defect was accompanied by chest wall vibration. With a large defect, the murmur was less intense (Table 13).

Table 7.

Clinical signs of VSD depending on the size of the defect							
Defect Size	Large (>4 mm)			Small (<4mm)			P
	N	n+	%	N	n+	%	
Perioral Cyanosis	45	34	75,6%	11	6	54,5%	P>0.05
Dyspnea	45	11	24,4%	11	1	9,1%	P>0.05
Pansystolic Murmur	45	34	75,6%	11	10	90,9%	P>0.05

In the main group, a non-restrictive type of VSD with a defect size of more than 4 mm was more frequently observed: 80.4% (45) compared to a small defect (less than 4 mm) - 19.6% (11). In the preoperative period, heart failure was identified in this group: in 9 (16.07%) children - stage I, in 42 (76.05%) - stage II A, and in 5 (8.9%) children - stage II B.

In the main group, the chest X-ray showed an enhanced pulmonary pattern due to the vascular component, and the cardiothoracic index was 61.0±4.4%.

Analysis showed significant differences in end-systolic dimension (ESD) and end-diastolic dimension

(EDD) between the main and control groups. The average ESD in the main group was 1.98±0.04 cm, which was significantly higher than in the control group (0.98±0.02 cm, P<0.001). Similarly, the average EDD in the main group was 2.99±0.07 cm, which also significantly exceeded the control group's value (1.99±0.06 cm, P<0.001). These differences indicate significant changes in the structure and function of the left ventricle in children with CHD, necessitating surgical correction. The sizes of the left and right atria, as well as the right ventricle, did not show statistically significant differences between the groups. The left atrium size in the main group was 2.03±0.03 cm, compared to 2.08±0.05

cm in the control group ($P>0.05$). The right atrium size was 2.01 ± 0.04 cm in the main group and 1.94 ± 0.06 cm in the control group ($P>0.05$). The right ventricle size also did not show significant differences: 1.0 ± 0.02 cm in the main group and 0.99 ± 0.02 cm in the control group ($P>0.05$). The left ventricular ejection fraction (EF) plays a significant role in determining the status, diagnosis, treatment, and prognosis of patients with heart failure. The average EF in the main group was $71.57\pm 1.48\%$, slightly higher than in the control group ($70.79\pm 1.97\%$, $P>0.05$). Despite the lack of significant differences in this indicator, the observed increase in EF in the main group may indicate compensatory mechanisms aimed at maintaining cardiac function in

the presence of structural anomalies (Table 14). These differences indicate significant changes in the structure and function of the left ventricle in children with CHD, necessitating surgical correction.

Thus, young children with VSD at the time of surgical treatment differ from healthy children in terms of physical development delay and disproportionality. They often have comorbid conditions such as anemia syndrome and malnutrition (WAZ). ECG shows changes in the heart axis and ventricular hypertrophy. Echocardiography records an enlargement of the left heart chambers. Given these pathological changes in children with VSD, thorough preoperative preparation is strongly recommended.

Table 8.

Main Echocardiographic Indicators in Examined Children

Indicator	Control group n=30	Main group n=56	P
End-Systolic Dimension (ESD), cm	$0,98\pm 0,02$	$1,98\pm 0,04$	P<0.001
End-Diastolic Dimension (EDD), cm	$1,99\pm 0,06$	$2,99\pm 0,07$	P<0.001
Left Atrium Size, cm	$2.08\pm 0,05$	$2,03\pm 0,03$	P>0.05
Right Atrium Size, cm	$1,94\pm 0,06$	$2,01\pm 0,04$	P>0.05
Right Ventricle Size, cm	$0,99\pm 0,02$	$1\pm 0,02$	P>0.05
Ejection Fraction (EF), %	$70,79\pm 1,97$	$71,57\pm 1,48$	P>0.05

Note: ESD - End-Systolic Dimension, EDD - End-Diastolic Dimension, EF - Ejection Fraction.

Conclusions.

1. The conducted studies showed that the biometric parameters of the fetal and newborn heart have specific features, including heart size, wall thickness, and the width of the ventricles and atria, which were considered in the diagnosis of VSD.

2. The main indications for multiparametric extended antenatal echocardiography of the fetus are maternal risk factors, abnormal images of the four-chamber view and the three-vessel view, and ambiguous results from standard ultrasound screening.

3. The severity of clinical and laboratory manifestations in children with VSD was directly proportional to the size of the defect and characterized by a polymorphism of symptoms such as cyanosis (75.6%), dyspnea during physical activity (24.4%), frequent respiratory infections, and protein-energy malnutrition (60.7%). At the same time, a pansystolic murmur was present in 75.6% of children, and its intensity was inversely proportional to the size of the defect: the larger the defect (>4.0 mm), the less intense the murmur.

4. The echocardiographic semiotics of fetal VSD were detailed depending on the variant and size of the defect.

5. The diagnostic accuracy of various echographic modes in diagnosing fetal VSD was 72.4% in B-mode, 83.6% when combined with color Doppler imaging, 90.5% with STIC, and 98.2% with Speckle Tracking.

Ethics approval and consent to participate

Informed consent was obtained from mothers to conduct the study.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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